

BEYOND OBJECT-BASED SORTING: WHY HETEROGENEOUS RIGID PP PACKAGING REQUIRES SYSTEMIC SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: *The Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) of the European Parliament and of the Council sets ambitious targets for the incorporation of recycled content in rigid polypropylene (PP) packaging, requiring 10 % in contact-sensitive applications and 35 % in all other packaging by 2030. Meeting these goals demands not only an expansion of recycling capacity but also significant improvements in recyclate quality. A key challenge lies in the inherent heterogeneity of post-consumer rigid PP waste, which comprises products with diverse processing methods, polymer grades, additives, and fillers. This study analyzes 19 representative rigid PP packaging products collected from an Austrian material recovery facility, covering bottles, trays, cups, tubs, and pails. Melt flow rate, tensile modulus, and Charpy notched impact strength were determined to evaluate material diversity and its implications for sorting strategies. The results reveal significantly higher melt flow rates for injection molded products compared to blow-molded and thermoformed packaging. Moreover, substantial variation in stiffness and impact strength due to PP types and application-specific requirements were found. To avoid mixed and intermediate recyclate properties, eco-efficient sorting strategies need to be developed, relying both on object- and flake-sorting. Object-based sorting can isolate distinct product categories and is indispensable for producing high-purity streams, such as those intended for food-contact recycling. However, its effectiveness is constrained by recognition limitations, unknown material formulations and product properties, multi-component designs, and contamination. Property-based flake sorting offers complementary advantages, including a higher spectral quality after pre-treatment and the potential for more accurate property-based separation, but requires robust prediction models linking spectral data to mechanical properties. Due to the scarcity in this field, future research should aim to close this gap. It can be concluded that neither sorting approach alone can deliver the range of recyclate properties needed to meet market demands. Instead, a systemic combination of object-based and flake-based sorting, supported by advanced property-prediction capabilities, is essential for developing a diversified PP recyclate portfolio in a resource-efficient manner.*

Keywords: mechanical recycling, property-based sorting, rigid polypropylene, post-consumer packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

The Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) of the European Parliament and of the Council sets ambitious targets for the incorporation of recycled materials in plastic packaging. For polypropylene (PP), one of the most widely used rigid packaging plastics in the EU27 + 3 region, the recycling content shall be at 10 % for contact-sensitive packaging and at 35 % for all other packaging by 2030 (European Parliament and the Council, 2025). Meeting these goals will necessitate not only expanded recycling capacities, but also substantial improvements in recycle quality to fulfill diverse and demanding product specifications (Plastics Recyclers Europe, 2023).

Achieving a closed-loop for rigid PP packaging is significantly complicated by the complexity of the waste stream, which contains a fluctuating mix of products with specifically tailored material formulations of all major processing methods (Eriksen et al., 2019; Geier et al., 2024a, Mager et al., 2023). Therefore, the challenge in PP recycling is to convert its heterogeneous feedstock into a diversified recycle portfolio. In pursuit of enhanced quality, sensor-based sorting is considered to be a critical point for intervention, which is already implemented at multiple stages of the recycling process (Kroell et al., 2022). Advanced object-based sorting offers distinct advantages compared to flake-based sorting, such as the isolation of food contact materials (AIM – European Brands Association, 2025). However, significantly reducing the feedstock heterogeneity from a material property perspective on object-level may not be feasible under ecoefficiency constraints (Van Camp et al., 2024).

Since specific grades and formulations (including additives and fillers) are not disclosed by manufacturers and material degradation during the production and use phase is unspecified, an initial property screening of post-consumer PP packaging waste was conducted in this study. Based on the obtained product-property matrix of nineteen different PP packaging products from the Austrian PP waste, limitations of advanced object-based sorting and advantages of flake-based sorting were identified.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Sample collection was conducted at an Austrian material recovery facility (MRF), where sorting of separately collected post-consumer lightweight packaging is conducted. The light-colored rigid PP stream was targeted, which was accessible at a conveyor belt prior to baling. The selection of suitable products for this study was limited to frequently occurring white and transparent packaging, so that the collection of a specific product (distinct brand and type in terms of, e.g., aroma or design) was feasible in sufficient quantities within a moderate time frame. Moreover, the product selection was aimed to cover all major applications of rigid PP packaging, as at least 2 kg of products from the categories bottles, trays, cups, tubs, and pails could be collected. However, no representative samples for lids, caps, and closures were obtained, primarily due to the abundant product variety and the low weight of certain products. Furthermore, a scarcity of caps and closures prevailed, as they were predominantly still attached to the primary packaging (e.g., high-density polyethylene bottles). A list of the investigated products is depicted in Table 1, including the processing method, color, and filling volume.

Table 1: Overview on investigated post-consumer rigid PP packaging products collected from the light-colored PP stream at an Austrian material recovery facility

Bottles		Trays		Cups		Tubs		Pails	
Product	Details	Product	Details	Product	Details	Product	Details	Product	Details
Bottle-A	blow molding, clear, 0.24 L	Tray-A	thermo-forming, clear, 0.20 L	Cup-A	thermo-forming, white, 0.20 L	Tub-A	injection molding, white, 0.20 L	Pail-A	injection molding, white, 1.00 L
Bottle-B	blow molding, clear, 0.25 L	Tray-B	thermo-forming, clear, 0.20 L	Cup-B	injection molding, white, 0.23 L	Tub-B	injection molding, clear, 0.50 L	Pail-B	injection molding, white, 1.00 L
Bottle-C	blow molding, clear, 3.75 L	Tray-C	injection-molding, white, 5.00 L	Cup-C	injection molding, white, 0.23 L	Tub-C	injection molding, white, 1.00 L	Pail-C	injection molding, white, 10.00 L
Bottle-D	blow molding, white, 4.50 L			Cup-D	thermo-forming, clear, 0.50 L	Tub-D	injection molding, clear, 1.00 L	Pail-D	injection molding, white, 10.00 L

2.2 Wet-mechanical treatment and sample preparation

In a first step, all removable parts (i.e., lids, labels, sealing film) were separated from the main PP body. The products were then pre-washed with cold water for 5 min in a PW 818 washing machine (Miele & Cie. KG, Gütersloh, Germany) with the addition of 0.5 % sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to reduce the overall contamination load. Subsequently, the products were coarsely shredded in a SM300 cutting mill (Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany) with a screen size of 20 mm. The following washing process consisted of a hot-washing step (60 °C, 2 % NaOH, 10 min) and a rinsing step (20 °C, 5 min). After drying for 8 h at 60 °C (LUXOR A, motan holding GmbH, Konstanz, Germany), the flake-size was reduced to 8 mm (SM 300, Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany), in order to facilitate direct injection molding. Multipurpose specimens and Type 1 specimens were produced according to ISO 19069-2:2024 via injection molding (Victory 60, ENGEL AUSTRIA GmbH, Schwertberg, Austria).

2.3 Characterization methods

Melt flow rate (MFR) measurements were conducted with an Aflow melt flow indexer (ZwickRoell, Ulm, Germany) according to ISO 1133-1:2022. Tests were performed using flakes at 230 °C with a load of 2.16 kg. Within one measurement, six cut-offs were made. Young's modulus was determined in tensile tests using an AllroundLine Z005 universal testing machine equipped with multi-extensometers (ZwickRoell, Ulm, Germany). According to ISO 527-1:2019 and ISO 527-2:2025, the traverse speed was set to 1 mm/min for the determination of the Young's modulus and 50 mm/min until failure. Five specimens were tested per material. Charpy notched impact strength (nIS) was obtained on an HIT25P pendulum impact tester (ZwickRoell, Ulm, Germany) equipped with a 2 J pendulum according to ISO 179-1:2023. Ten specimens were notched and tested in edgewise blow direction.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Properties of investigated PP packaging products

Since the data presented in this work is limited to three material parameters, a three-dimensional graphical display would be feasible. However, two separate graphs were chosen due to an enhanced visibility, with the MFR being the common feature in both, as it allows the grouping of the main

processing methods at certain MFR ranges. Thus, the correlation between tensile modulus and MFR is displayed in Figure 1, while the correlation between Charpy notched impact strength is depicted in Figure 2. Blow molding products are found to have the lowest melt flow rates (2.1 – 4.9 g/10 min), followed by thermoformed products (6.6 – 8.4 g/10 min). Even though the investigated sample set does not show overlaps between blow-molded and thermoformed products in terms of MFR, it can be assumed that there would be overlaps to a certain extent in a larger sample set. Contrary to these low-MFR products, injection molding grades in rigid PP packaging were found to have significantly higher melt flow rates, which were measured between 56.1 g/10 min and 90.4 g/10 min.

The analysis of tensile modulus and Charpy nIS sheds light on the usage of homo- and copolymers in the investigated products, which are required to fulfill demanding product specifications. Especially the reduction of material in packaging necessitates optimized material properties, so that, e.g., a lower wall thickness is compensated by a higher stiffness of the material. In that case, nucleated homopolymers with an enhanced stiffness are a frequent choice. This becomes evident for Cup-A and Cup-D, which are both thermoformed cups without a specialized design for increased stability, exhibiting tensile moduli of 1990 MPa and 1710 MPa, respectively. In contrast, the lowest tensile moduli were obtained for the investigated bottles (800 – 1040 MPa), for which random copolymers are commonly used. Their advantage of having a high impact strength (6.8 – 10.5 kJ/m²) comes at the cost of having a lower tensile modulus. For trays, tubs, and injection molded cups intermediate tensile modulus values were obtained, yet covering a significantly large range from 1220 MPa to 1610 MPa. In general, clear products exhibit a lower tensile modulus, which is in accordance with Kuhn et al. (2025), and can be explained by a higher probability of random copolymers. The results of Charpy impact testing apart from bottles show that the majority of products lies in the range of 4.0 kJ/m² to 7.0 kJ/m². Notable exceptions are Cup-A and Tub-D, with 3.4 kJ/m² and 9.3 kJ/m², respectively. Since Cup-A is most likely a highly-stiff homopolymer, the low impact strength is not surprising. Tub-D, on the other hand, is an ice cream packaging, which explains the high impact strength, as it is required for sub-zero temperatures to maintain product safety. A balance of stiffness and increased impact strength is commonly only achieved with block copolymers, which Tub-D can be attributed to.

Figure 1: Tensile modulus over melt flow rate of the investigated rigid PP packaging products.

Figure 2: Charpy notched impact strength over melt flow rate for the investigated rigid PP packaging products.

3.2 Towards systemic solutions for enhancing PP recyclate quality through improved sorting

The material characteristics of the investigated packaging products clearly underline the diversity of grades and formulations that are present in the post-consumer rigid PP waste stream. To avoid mixed and intermediate recyclate properties, eco-efficient sorting strategies need to be developed, relying both on object- and flake-sorting.

Enhancing the sorting depth on an object-level bears the potential to isolate distinct products of the waste stream. This can either be implemented to exclude sources of severe contamination (e.g., silicon cartridges), or to generate a feedstock of defined products. Especially for obtaining highly-pure streams intended for food-contact recycling, sorting on object-level is indispensable. Furthermore, the potential of creating specified recyclates by object recognition could be demonstrated by Geier et al. (2024b), who obtained a low-MFR by sorting out blow-molded bottles. However, AI recognition is mainly limited to the products the system was trained on, and the recognition can be impeded by contamination, fragmentation, and agglomeration. In recent years, digital watermarks and the use of tracers have gained attention to enhance the accuracy in object recognition. While these systems are promising in theory, a comprehensive and unanimous application would be a prerequisite, which the authors consider unlikely without appropriate incentives or legislation. Moreover, the exact material properties of a product will predominantly be unknown, as they are not disclosed by the manufacturer, and non-separated multi-component products (e.g., injection-molded tub with thermoformed lid) will inevitably be sorted incorrectly from a property perspective. Finally, other potential disadvantages of splitting the rigid PP waste stream at object-level are separate logistics and wet-mechanical treatment for each fraction. Hence, either a batch process with intermediate bunkers or parallel washing lines are required.

As a fitting counterpart, property-based flake-sorting would allow for the feedstock to be processed as a whole in wet-mechanical treatment. Therefore, the throughput can be maximized and the reduced bulk density after shredding would be beneficial if intermediate bunker systems are required.

Nevertheless, a clear verdict regarding the preferred sorting option for a resource-efficient wet-mechanical treatment is not possible, since the appropriate setup and its scaling can be adjusted accordingly. The main challenge in effectively using flake-sorting for the diversification of recyclate properties is the correlation of spectral data and the corresponding material characteristics. While there are already approaches to determine MFR and density for polyethylene high-density, comparable research for PP is scarce. Therefore, future research should aim to close this gap by developing robust prediction models for material properties from spectral data. Flake-sorting has the upside that the overall spectral quality is significantly higher due to the removal of contaminants, films, labels, and also printing inks. Additionally, the scattering of flakes and the potentially higher spectral resolution in flake-sorting contribute to the data quality. Contrary to conventional flake-sorting, where the efficiency is highest if only a small percentage of contamination needs to be removed, spectral sorting according to direct material properties may require the positive sorting of a larger percentage of flakes, as well as multiple sorting steps. Hence, the setup will likely involve a flake sorter cascade, aimed to diversify PP recyclates in a resource-efficient manner.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the investigated post-consumer products, the diversity of material grades that prevail in the rigid PP packaging stream could be demonstrated. The assessed product parameters lie the foundation for the development of robust property prediction models from spectral data, which are required to implement flake-sorting as a key technology for the diversification of PP recyclates. Once such prediction models become available, cost-efficient strategies for clustering materials by property profile will be needed, considering the practical limitation of simultaneous sorting fractions.

Meeting the PPWR targets for recycled content will require PP recyclates tailored to demanding applications, including food-contact packaging. The results presented here underline that this goal can only be achieved through a systemic combination of object-based and flake-based sorting, leveraging the specific strengths of each approach. Object-sorting ensures the removal or isolation of defined product categories, while flake-sorting enables refined property-based separation at scale.

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5 REFERENCES

AIM – European Brands Association (2025). Holy Grail 2.0. <https://www.digitalwatermarks.eu/> (last accessed: 30.07.2025)

European Parliament and the Council (2025). Regulation (EU) 2025/40 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 December 2024 on packaging and packaging waste, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2019/904, and repealing Directive 94/62/EC. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2025/40> (last accessed: 30.07.2025)

Eriksen, M. K., Christiansen, J. D., Daugaard, A. E., & Astrup, T. F. (2019). Closing the loop for PET, PE and PP waste from households: Influence of material properties and product design for plastic recycling. *Waste Management*, 96, 75-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.07.005>

Geier, J., Bredács, M., Witschnigg, A., Vollprecht, D., Oreski, G. (2024a). Analysis of different polypropylene waste bales: Evaluation of the source material for PP recycling. *Waste Management & Research*, 42(9), 767-775. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X241227369>

Geier, J., Barretta, C., Hinczica, J., Haar, B., Bredács, M., Witschnigg, A., Mayrbäurl, E., & Oreski, G. (2024b). Feasibility study on the production of low melt flow rate recycled polypropylene from postconsumer waste. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 141(30), Article e55694. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.55694>

Kroell, N., Chen, X., Greiff, K., Feil, A. (2022). Optical sensors and machine learning algorithms in sensor-based material flow characterization for mechanical recycling processes: A systematic literature review. *Waste Management*, 149, 259-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2022.05.015>

Kuhn, N., Mager, M., Fischer, J., Koinig, G., & Tischberger-Aldrian, A. (2025). Increasing the PP-recyclate quality by enhanced mechanical processing of post-consumer packaging waste. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 223, 108494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2025.108494>

Mager, M., Berghofer, M., & Fischer, J. (2023). Polyolefin Recyclates for Rigid Packaging Applications: The Influence of Input Stream Composition on Recyclate Quality. *Polymers*, 15(13), 2776. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15132776>

Plastics Recyclers Europe (2023). HDPE & PP Rigids Market in Europe: State of play, data 2023. <https://www.plasticsrecyclers.eu/publications/> (last accessed: 30.07.2025)

Van Camp, N., Lase, I. S., De Meester, S., Hoozée, S., & Ragaert, K. (2024). Exposing the pitfalls of plastics mechanical recycling through cost calculation. *Waste Management*, 189, 300–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2024.08.017>